

Can Blockchain technology help prevent food shortages and food surplus in exceptional circumstances?

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 has had an enormous global impact on several industries, companies but also people. The pandemic has divided us but has also challenged us to think outside of the box. Humans have come up with more creative ideas and solutions to problems that probably wouldn't have occurred in the first place. As for this paper we want to focus on what a global pandemic can learn or teach us, instead of what it has taken from us. One of the biggest industries in the world, the food industry, had to challenge a lot of different problems during this global pandemic. This paper aims to focus on how these problems can be solved using block-chain based technologies. In other words: How can Blockchain technologies help to prevent food shortages and food surplus in the food industry? This paper uses two perspectives to answer this question. The first perspective is the Business Process Integration perspective. The second one is the IT Governance perspective. To conclude this paper, two examples of the use of block-chain based technologies in the food industry are given.

Keywords

Covid-19, Food Industry, Blockchain, Technology

INTRODUCTION

During the COVID-19 era, it has been easier and more accessible to shop and buy online for customers. This is caused by the decrease in social activities, commuting and the digitization in the value chain. Therefore, spending has been decreased and made shopping easier for the customers. Unfortunately, not all businesses were ready for this abrupt digitization. The impact on the global economy has been tremendous. Necessary restrictions have been made to limit the consequences of COVID-19, such as closing down shops or restaurants. These restrictions also have implications for businesses, including reduction of

business activities and supply chain disruptions (Papadopoulos, T., Baltas, K. N., & Balta, M. E., 2020).

There are four frameworks across different development studies, which indicate how the COVID-19 pandemic further highlights the requirement for embracing a global development approach. According to (Oldekop, Johan A., et al., 2020), these four frameworks are: global value chains (GVCs), digitalization, debt, and climate change.

The future of what value chains will look like, post COVID-19, has consequences for every sector. The degree and nature of rebuilding these value chains post-pandemic will have crucial implications for inclusion, quantity and quality of jobs, as well as sustainability transitions.

According to all the radical changes the world is undergoing, it has become clear that the ability of governments, industry and wider society rely on IS technology to operate and function within and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

RESEARCH

Extreme disruptions like a pandemic, have devastating impacts on business and supply chain. Therefore, this results in a decrease of efficiency, profitability and survival. This effect gets multiplied as manufacturing, services and commerce are globally connected. (Papadopoulos et al., 2017)

Not only COVID-19, but also from past pandemics it has been shown that quarantines and panic have a huge impact on the world economy. Therefore, automatically the effects of a pandemic occur in agricultural activities.

When there is an outbreak of a virus, there is additionally an expansion in hunger (Burgui, 2020).

There are many uncertainties now in the agricultural sector. Farmers are hesitating whether they should start planting and how much they need to plant. Since they are forced to store the unsold product for a longer period. This leads to a reduction in the food quality and an increase in the cost of production, as the agricultural sector is extremely perishable. Also, one of the main agricultural issues are the difficulties of getting inputs such as; seeds, fertilizers and insecticides. At the beginning of 2020, 135 million people were already facing extreme hunger. According to the World Food Program, this could rise to 265 million people by the end of this year [see figure below].

Figure 1. CSIS - Food insecurity statistics

After this hit from COVID-19, the agriculture businesses realized the decreasing demand for their produce. Since these products are significant for agricultural diversification, multiple market avenues such as e-platforms should be strengthened to minimize risk during a shock. Thus, it will crash prices and increase farmers' losses.

Sector

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to significant social and economic implications after his outbreak in December 2019. So, both the food and agriculture sector were also affected by this pandemic. Due to the 'global crisis' the demand in the agricultural sector fell, which led to a price drop of 20% in agricultural commodities (Nicola et al., 2020, p. 191).

As the disease progresses, the situation gets worse, with for example: developing restrictions. Therefore, labor shortages for the harvest are caused and troubles for farmers for bringing their products to the market. In other words, creating more restrictions for agriculture.

According to the 'Food and Agriculture Organization', COVID-19 affects agriculture in two significant ways (FAO, 2020). These two ways are the supply and demand for food, which are directly related to food security. In this manner, the food demand becomes smaller and the accessibility becomes interrupted and gets more difficult.

COVID-19 has a big impact on the activities and actions of humanity, where agriculture is also

affected. Demand for food is hugely affected by the disease due to restrictions in mobility, reduced buying power, and with a huge effect on the vulnerable population. Due to these dramatic changes and impacts, governments are forced to take more radical measures to stop the spread, likewise affecting the worldwide food system. The reason for the measures ought to be to ensure health and food security, to control the impact on economic growth.

COVID-19 has shown how digital technologies can improve the functioning of supply chains and be more efficient. With digital technology, problems can be forecast, and temporary shortages can be managed to preserve food chains. New technologies could encourage the supply-demand interface, which would be particularly important for supply chains of highly perishable goods. Agricultural farmers have confronted more concerning issues than have other farmers in harvesting and selling their yields.

METHODS

This paper aimed to provide the reader with in-depth information about how Blockchain technologies can help to prevent food shortages and food surplus in the food industry. This paper will include the following three types of information management perspectives in the analysis: IT governance analyses, business process integration and cyber security.

In order to reach the aim of this paper, a literature review is conducted. Also, two examples of the use of block-chain based technologies in the food industry are given.

IT GOVERNANCE

The presence of digital transformation in the agriculture sector is certainly an exceedingly development. Another recognizable pattern is a concentration of market power among significant input suppliers. Key organizations among corporations active in the agricultural sector have been progressively utilized in recent years to gain by Big Data created in the sector. These advancements raise concerns regarding IT governance, resulting in more challenges of potential abuses of market power from input suppliers and also about potential discrimination of particular farming systems and practices. Currently the products of agriculture businesses are primarily directed towards large area farms and large agricultural companies equipped with advanced machinery and tools (Kosior, K. 2018).

In the new paradigm of smart farming, there is a risk. The risk is that this new paradigm might lead to the displacement of smaller farmers, potentially decreasing the diversity of food and farming domains (Bronson, 2018).

Digitization might indeed tackle numerous issues in agriculture. Simultaneously, unclear property rights to agricultural data, growing market power of input suppliers and uneven distribution of benefits gathering from digitization might prompt unwanted developments in the sector. There is in this manner a need for value-embedded research about desired directions of digital transformation (Kosior, K. 2018).

Farming is said to be undergoing a “smart” technology “revolution” (Datafloq, 2015).

While there are without doubt opportunities related with smart farming, there are potentially negative outcomes, especially socio-ethical implications. One of the main ethical issues is the mining of health data. We can infer that the use of environmental Big Data gathered will present challenges in determining which data to collect in order to meet societal goals and not just corporate goals, and also determining how much access to societally important datasets to enable. The ‘Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition (GODAN) calls for open access to agricultural data as a fundamental right since they feel it will help with the pressing of a crisis that is global food insecurity. The majority of research on innovation and society would suggest that, regardless of what we think about smart farming, it is inevitable that it will have both benefits and risks (Bronson, K., 2018).

Governance Design Matrix

To decide who is responsible for making IT governance decisions, the Governance Design Matrix (Weill, 2004) can be used. This matrix distinguishes six different archetypes, namely: business monarchy, IT monarchy, feudal, federal, IT duopoly and anarchy. In a business monarchy, senior business executives make the decisions. In an IT monarchy, IT professionals make the decisions. The feudal model is a bit more complicated but not very common. In the feudal model typically the business unit, region or function is responsible for IT Governance decisions. This is based upon the traditions of old England, where princes and princesses make their own decisions based on what it best for their kingdom. The federal model is the model in which business enterprise wide executives and business unit executives or members come together and make IT governance decisions. The IT duopoly is a two-party arrangement where decisions represent agreement between IT executives and one business group. And lastly, the anarchy, where individuals or very small groups make their own decisions based only on their own needs.

Using this matrix for the agri-food sector could benefit enterprises in this sector to govern their IT decisions better and more effective. Based upon the fact that the supply and demand of food is currently

a global matter, the IT duopoly is the best archetype for businesses in the agricultural sector. If only the business executives would make the decisions, blockchain based technologies would be implemented only for the purpose of their own company or business unit. Enabling more efficiency in for example their administrative processes. If only the IT people would have something to say about the IT governance decisions, probably a lot of new IT or new techniques would be implemented without letting the business having a say in this. The business probably has enough concerns or focus points that the IT department(s) would miss out of enthusiasm. The feudal model wouldn’t work for the agri-food sector, enabling every company to do whatever fits themselves best, would not prevent global food shortages or surpluses. This needs to be governed worldwide. The federal model doesn’t include any IT people and is therefore not useful for the agri-food businesses. Blockchain technology is already complicated enough and therefore it needs support and understanding from IT departments. Lastly, the anarchy archetype, where everyone does what they think is best. Because this food supply and demand is a global problem, applying the anarchy archetype would result in a catastrophe. So, the IT duopoly would fit the agricultural sector the best. Namely because this includes business and IT together and enables a successful cooperation between critical businesspeople and innovative and enthusiast IT-people.

BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

Several works regarding the blockchain are present in the literature, but few of those concern agricultures and even less report experimental applications. (Casado-Vara et al., 2018) proposes a new simulation model for agriculture tracing implementing blockchain and multi-agent systems. In this model, the current agriculture supply chain approach as a linear model starts from manufacturers and imports to seller and food service in correlation with a decentralized supply chain structured on blockchain architecture and the multi-agent frameworks.

Figure 2. Overview supply chain food sector

Figure 3. Supply Chain including Block Chain

(A) Current agriculture supply chain model as a linear model from producers and imports to retailer and foodservice;

(B) supply chain including blockchain architecture and the multi-agent systems. Modified from Casado-Vara et al. (2018).

In the next figure below, an UML-model in the agricultural sector is pictured, with the blockchain framework developed. The lower part shows how a decentralized blockchain based framework can increase the product safety within the supply chain management. This is accomplished with a higher efficiency provided by the traceability system recording all the occasions occurring and monitoring security and quality (Casado-Vara et al., 2018).

Figure 4. UML Model

Pre- and Post Covid-19 further analyses

For quite a long-time agroecologist have cautioned that industrial agriculture turned out to be too limited ecologically, highly reliant on outside inputs, and incredibly vulnerable to diseases, climate change and to a pandemic, like the current Covid-19 situation which led to a complete shutdown.

Wheat, rice and corn are the three harvest species which provide half of the calories consumed globally. This includes a low value diet, which fundamentally impacts the food security, nutritional status and health. Many countries are losing their food security during this pandemic as the corporate globalized food system has disrupted the food production managed by laborers. This led to the consequence of a shift from traditional various and rich diets to highly processed and energy dense food. Obesity and diet related chronic diseases have multiplied during this pandemic.

Covid-19 has uncovered the socio-ecological fragility of current industrial-globalized food systems and the effects on farming. Food supply chains raise concerns about widespread food shortages. There is an urgent need (relevant for post Covid-19) for a transition to more ecologically tough and localized food systems.

The world is now in a transformational change in agriculture accompanied by a shift from a market economy to a solidarity economy, from fossil fuels to renewable energies, from big corporations to cooperatives, and so forth. Social movements will be leading in the post covid-19 world which are aware that a pre Covid-19 world situation is not an option. Rather they will be effectively involved in developing local alternatives to unite sustainable and healthy agriculture (Altieri, M. A., & Nicholls, C. I., 2020).

The challenge before Covid-19 was to change our agricultural systems to meet multiple sustainability objectives simultaneously. Now, the unavoidable after the Covid-19 pandemic, is to produce healthy and nutritious food, but also improving soil health, cleaning our waters, restoring biodiversity, improving farm labor conditions, revive local economies and so on. In reshaping and reforming our agriculture, we may not only grow the food that we need, but also the shared social space that our democracy badly needs (Meine, C., 2020).

CYBER SECURITY

New technologies bring new challenges and risks. From recent research (Feng et al., 2020, p. 13), several challenges have come up. One of them is the vulnerability of smart contracts. According to (Alharby and van Moorsel, 2017) it is challenging to make up bugs in deployed smart contract. This is caused due to the irreversibility of blockchains. Furthermore, another challenge is the choice of the consensus algorithm (Zheng et al., 2018a). This is a process in computer science used to achieve agreement on a single data value among distributed processes or systems. Next, the data accessibility and integrity for distributed ledger systems is a

challenge. Reyna et al. (2018) endorses that ensuring the security and integrity of input data is very difficult. Lastly, data security is also a challenge. This challenge is substantiated by the fact that 51% of computation power is not safe (Khan and Salah, 2018) and there is a high probability of traceability transaction modification for data malleability (Kumar and Mallick, 2018).

When implementing blockchain based technologies these technological challenges should be considered. If the agri-food sector decides to use these technologies more, experts should take these security issues into account.

CURRENT BLOCKCHAIN SOLUTIONS IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

According to Tripoli & Schmidhuber distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) have the potential to transform the global food system by introducing important efficiency gains along value chains, and improving trust, transparency and traceability (Tripoli & Schmidhuber, 2018, p. V). Tripoli and Schmidhuber (2018) name several examples of how DLT's are currently used in the food industry. These examples explain how these technologies are used to lower the uncertainty during the exchange of value. The use of DLTs removes third party intermediaries, reduces transaction costs, enables faster and even real-time transactions, assures immutable data entries and provides access to the database for all participants in the network. A good example of an efficiency gain is the example of the World Food Programme (WFP). They have piloted cash transfers programmes using blockchain-based technology. It was used to record supermarket transactions in a Syrian refugee camp. This pilot provided financial savings for the World Food Programme. This facilitated elimination of financial intermediaries, the associated transaction fees and the time WFP accountants spent on compiling data and reports from banks and stores. The blockchain-based technology enabled automated record-keeping, which resulted in the benefits stated above.

The second example is an example of more transparency in the agriculture supply chain process. According to (Tripoli & Schmidhuber, 2018, p. 2) transactions in the agriculture supply chain are inherently risky and complex, this is caused by the transaction relying on a high number of intermediaries. This results in less transparency for the consumer on how and where their food is produced. A way to increase this transparency is using DLTs to track foods from point A to B. A group of big food companies: Dole, Driscoll, Golden State Foods, Kroger, McCormick and Company, Nestlé, Tyson Foods and Walmart have teamed up with IBM to use these technologies. They have

teamed up to enable more transparency in their supply chain, enable improvement of traceability of their products and to streamline payments. A perfect example of improvement in traceability of products is the partnership of Walmart and IBM. They tracked a package of mangoes from the shelf of the retailer back to the farmer in a matter of seconds using blockchain-based technologies.

These examples are a good representation of how blockchain-based technologies can enhance the agriculture supply chain. In times of a pandemic or a global crisis the demand and supply of food needs to be more aligned. Blockchain-based technologies can enable and facilitate this alignment. Furthermore, these technologies have more benefits like traceability of transactions and of products.

DISCUSSION

In the discussion we would like to address three different discussion points. First, the new technologies as discussed above would benefit the smaller and medium-sized companies. They would benefit from the fact that there is more transparency in the agri-food market. It would enable the smaller companies in the sector to be able to do business with each other without long and complicated contracts. On the other hand, the bigger companies do benefit from these contracts. If blockchain technologies would enable a platform where the supply and demand in the agri-food sector would be monitored and displayed, the big companies would be disadvantaged. Right now, the bigger companies in the sector already have current contracts. These contracts are mostly on a long-term basis. Introducing a platform as discussed above would trigger these companies who have running contracts with other big companies. This is a way for these companies to secure their market position. Sometimes the lack of transparency is better for the bigger companies to do business. So, the first discussion point is the fact that large companies would try to stop the use of blockchain technologies who would enable platforms like these.

The second discussion point is security. Currently contracts are being managed by the agri-food businesses themselves. If contracts will be managed in a blockchain matter by the platform, companies would probably have security concerns. Farmers already have some challenges with new technology, mostly because farming is a more non-digital market. Explaining the new blockchain technologies to these farmers would be challenging. Also persuading these farmers into using this technology to enable their business would be a challenge in itself. Furthermore, the security issues with making everything digital is a concern that these farmers would have but would also interest the purchaser and transport companies. Transparency in

the market would enable companies to trade more efficiently, but where sensitive data now mostly is kept between companies, data would now be available to outsiders. Also making use of the blockchain technologies makes the use of them prone to breaches and hackers that want to profit from the data negatively.

Finally, as discussed above, putting these blockchain technologies into work would require a lot of manpower, time and money. To set up a platform where supply and demand would be monitored globally, it requires a lot of partnerships all over the world. Food crosses all borders but countries would need to be willing to work together to enable such a big cooperation. This is only possible if all countries and global agri-food organizations or institutes know how they would benefit from all working together via this platform.

In short, the business-oriented application of blockchain technologies could benefit companies or perhaps networks directly. Companies themselves can decide whether they want to use this technology and they would be able to govern this themselves. The companies that do not want to take this risk or invest in these kinds of technologies would work in an old-fashioned way. Enabling a global cooperation between the whole agri-food sector to govern and manage the supply and demand of food, would be more challenging.

CONCLUSION

During this research we have learned about the consequences of Covid-19 in general, but especially in the Agricultural and Food industry. The world trade is hit strongly by this pandemic. We see that the impact on the food industry is significant. Beside the Covid-19 part, we also learned about technologies, such as Blockchain. We first had some struggles to find a suitable technology for the food industry which could help solving a major issue. After a few conversations with the lecturers of Tilburg University, we decided to focus on Blockchain technology. All this information is associated with BPI, IT Governance and Cyber Security perspective.

During the research we noticed that the overall food industry is lagging behind in terms of technology. Smart technologies, such as Blockchain or Smart Contracts can have significant impact. However, we also noticed that the food industry is very difficult to evaluate with technology because of issues such as shelf life and life cycle of the product. We think more time is needed to find out on how to implement Smart Technologies in the food industry. Because of the explanatory reasons for this research, we recommend conducting a detailed study on this subject. Another shortcoming of this research is the limited view on Cyber Security. A possible follow-

up research should pay more attention to Cyber Security compared to our study.

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